

DEVELOPMENT OF SPIRITUAL COMPETENCE IN HIS STUDENTS

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Annotation

Education based on a competency approach forms in students independence, having an active civil position, initiative, being able to use mediareours and information and communication technologies wisely in their activities, consciously choosing a profession, healthy competition and universal skills. This struggle, once evil and once Cultural in appearance, gives a thoughtful look around each of us, motivates to sum up the processes of the world's peat with reason and contemplation.

Keywords

social activity, competence, education, positivity, initiative, mediareurs, Information Communication, Technology, profession, competition.

On the implementation of the tasks set out at the Youth Forum of Uzbekistan on December 25, 2020 and at the appeal to the Supreme Assembly of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 29, 2020 and at the videoselector meeting held on January 19 of this year on the issues of radical improvement of the spiritual and educational system, strengthening the cooperation of state and public organizations in this regard, the

Spirituality and enlightenment have been an unequal power, happiness, peace, creativity, criterion of harmony, spiritual purification and soul-raising blessing in all times. Because he urged the nation, the people, so to speak, to live according to high qualities, moral criteria for maturation, to be always awake in the path of good without becoming a captive of selfishness, vanity, to make this world prosperous, to be burdened with beauty.

Based on the continuity of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the orientation towards the upbringing of a harmonious personality, in order to ensure the consistency of the content of subjects taught in the general secondary, secondary special, vocational training, base competencies and private competencies based on the content of each educational subject were established.

As you know, young people, and in general, the formation of the spiritual maturation of the future generation, our national and spiritual foundations, which serve to find a worthy place in society as a person, will be a didactic weapon in our total efforts. The rich heritage of our ancestors, such as imam Isa Termiziy, Imam Ghazzali, Hakim at-Termiziy, Khwaja Ahmad Yassawi, Khwaja Bahawuddin Naqshband, Kaykowus, Alisher Navoi, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, Mirzo Ulughbek, represents the fundamental basis of the events that have been practically introduced in this regard. Whereas spiritual education in its nature reflects the historical, national-cultural concept of each nation. The essence of the cultural-historical concept of personality was put forward by scientists and expressed in the following thoughts: "the behavior of a modern (civilized) person does not only remain the result of development in childhood, but is also a product of historical progress. Human development in the historical process has not only changed and developed socially, but also in the content of the relationship between man and nature, but both man himself and his nature have changed and developed." [5] today, under the influence of globalization, economic and political integration, the world is becoming increasingly holistic and a whole character profession. Not only the flow of capital and goods, even the scope of human action is expanding. Selfishness, lack of responsibility, selfishness, spread among people. Now it is becoming an important task for today to make a decision on the culture of immorality, intolerance, intolerance, elimination of manifestations among people, decency in society, humanism, tolerance, peace-loving, as well as promoting mutual respect, sincere friendship among people.

Communicative aspect of competence (motivational and regulatory framework for collection). experience of intercultural communication) education developed on the basis of an interactive approach. It represents the most modern form of active educational methods, based on the rules of the communicative approach. Interactive teaching methods are aimed at "the wide interaction of students not only with the teacher, but also with each other, the predominance of students' activities and the activation of internal communication (the existing experience of students of educational material)." The role of the teacher is to manage and support the activity of high-sif students in intercultural communication to reveal the diversity of points of view, facilitate the mutual understanding of communication participants, motivate them to internal communication, he acts as a consultant-facilitator (assistant).

Forms of interactive Organization of the educational process are social and psychodrama, education, business and role-playing game, discussion; Interactive is

achieved by stimulating thinking, stimulating empathic understanding of intercultural communication situations, referring to the life experience of interaction participants, substantiating the objective meaning and personal significance of certain situations, phenomena, processes, using dialogical (polylogical) learning methods.

Solving educational problems can only be within the framework of training and involves self-instruction, and also involves the development of presentations in different forms.

Projects that correspond to the content of the task and characterize the way to solve the main thing are its problematic state. According to the type of activity and the form of presentation of results, there are:

- constructive and practical projects, such as the Diary of observations, the creation of the game and its description;
- play-role-playing projects, such as professional activities to play parts of social interaction;
- informative research projects on a specific professional or social topic;
- scenario projects-scenario of an event related to cultural exchange;
- Creative Works-free literary composition, description of the solution of any problems, reflection on a professional topic.

The concepts of "confrontation" and "problem", in particular, active learning, business and role-playing games, embodied in technology, can be considered as forms of implementation.

Active educational technology is understood as the organization of the educational process, in which all students are forcibly involved in educational and cognitive activities, since each of them performs its functions, will have to report, or the quality of performing a collective task directly depends on the effectiveness of its work.

Without going into this issue in detail, we note that the most effective methods of organizing multicultural classes of upper-class students are the techniques of mnemonic activity, methods of life training, techniques of emotional impact, methods of explanation and discussion, etc. In accordance with the essence of the competency - based approach, the educational process involves the superior use of project, educational and Game forms of education and education, and in accordance with the essence of multicultural competence-social events involving the intercultural interaction of cultural and participants from the palace.

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